

The Reaction between Iodine and Oxalic Acid in Ethylene Glycol as a Solvent (A Preliminary Note).

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The reaction between oxalic acid or an oxalate and iodine has been much studied by Dhar and co-workers (*cf.* Dhar, "The Chemical Action of Light." p. 156), by Berthoud and Bellenot (*J. chim. Phys.*, 1924, 21, 308) and very recently by Griffith and McKeown (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28, 518) in water as the medium. Difference in opinion, however, exists between the various workers as to the exact mechanism of the reaction. The present authors, therefore, made an attempt to study the reaction in a non aqueous solvent, *i.e.*, ethylene glycol, but all attempts to make these react in the solvent, have been fruitless.

The reaction was studied both in dark and in light from a thousand watt lamp of tungsten filament in presence as well as in absence of water. The percentage of water used was 50 and 30 of the reaction mixture by volume. The substance failed to react even in presence of water,

The reactions were carried out at 31°. When attempts were made to study the reaction at high temperatures it was found that iodine attacked the solvent (glycol).

The results show that although iodine and oxalic acid are soluble in glycol yet they fail to react in the dark as well as in the total light from a thousand watt lamp. This is a curious phenomenon considering the fact that in water these two substances react with a measurable velocity. Our experiments prove, however, that the reaction between oxalic acid and iodine is truly ionic in character. According to Berthoud and Bellenot (*loc. cit.*) the following reactions take place in water.

From the above equations it will be seen that the reaction is independent of the medium, *i.e.*, the water does not enter into the chemical equations. If this were the case, the reaction should have taken place even in glycol.

From this point of view, the views of Griffith and McKeown (*loc. cit.*) seem to be correct (*vide infra*). According to them the reaction although truly ionic is not independent of the medium. Iodine is transformed first to IOH before it enters into the reaction,

But this raises the important question why the iodine-oxalic acid mixture in glycol fails to react even in the presence of water, or in what way does the glycol prevent the ionisation (if this is the primary process) of both the reactants. In the opinion of the authors the molecules of iodine as well as those of oxalic acid are closely surrounded by clusters of glycol molecules and although glycol itself is soluble in water, in presence of water, these clusters or structures are not sufficiently separated from the iodine or oxalic acid molecules for them to ionise as in aqueous solution. It is strange that both heat and light fail to ionise their molecules in glycol.

Glycol is very similar in properties to water. Almost all substances soluble in water are soluble in glycol also. Moreover, it contains in its molecule two 'OH' groups and its electrical conductivity is slightly greater than that of water (Critical Tables, Vol. VI, pp. 142, 152). If IOH formation is the primary process there is a greater chance of its formation in glycol than in water. Water itself is only slightly ionised. Hence if IOH formation is favoured in glycol, the reaction ought to be faster in glycol than in water. The above experiments have proved definitely that the reaction between oxalic acid and iodine is not independent of the medium in which it is carried out. The medium should be such that ionisation of the reactants must take place. The formation of an intermediate compound seems evident. The nature of the intermediate compound is not yet evident to the authors, but the suggested view of IOH formation is certainly doubtful,

A more exhaustive work is being carried out in these laboratories in which the action of the solvents is being studied.